

Photosynthesis of Amino Acids.

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It is generally believed by plant physiologists that synthesis of proteins in plants can take place even in the dark, provided carbohydrates are available and nitrogen assimilation by plants is not a photochemical process.

In order to test this point, we have tried to synthesise *in vitro* amino acids by exposing to sunlight solutions of glucose or glycol and nitrates in presence of different catalysts and photosensitisers and results are recorded in this paper. The detection and estimation of amino acids have been satisfactorily described by Mitchell and Hamilton ("Biochemistry of Amino Acids," 1929).

Small amounts of amino acids can be detected and estimated colorimetrically by the triketohydrindene hydrate, also known as "ninhydrin"

A blue colour develops when this reagent is mixed with an amino acid containing one free carboxyl and a free amino group in the α -position and the mixture heated. This reaction is sensitive to the extent of one part of an α -amino acid dissolved in 15,000 to 80,000 parts of water. With ammonium hydroxide and ninhydrin, a yellow or red colour is obtained. Ammonium salts, urea, uric acid and hippuric acid form a faint yellow coloration with ninhydrin. Concentrated solutions of alcohols, aldehydes, ketones and reducing sugars cause a red colour with ninhydrin and this disappears on cooling or dilution. The blue colour produced with amino acids and ninhydrin appears to be of colloidal nature and hence in this test an excess of neutral salts has to be avoided. Addition of pyridine seems necessary as it acts as a buffer and keeps the colouring matter in solution. With this valuable reagent, the amounts of amino acids obtained photosynthetically could be estimated colorimetrically by a Duboscq colorimeter according to the method of Harding and McLean (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1915, 20, 217; 1916, 24, 503). The test is ordinarily applied in the following way:— Dissolve 0.1 g. ninhydrin in 100 c.c. of water and prepare a 10% solu-

tion of pyridine in water. 1 C.c. of the solution containing the amino acid is mixed with 1 c.c. of the ninhydrin solution and 1 c.c. of the pyridine solution and the mixture heated in a test tube in boiling water for 20 minutes and if an amino acid is present, a bluish or bluish violet colour develops. On comparing the tint obtained with a standard solution of glutamic acid, which is quite stable in the dark, the amount of amino acids photosynthesised could be estimated. The glutamic acid (B.D.H.) used in these experiments, was free from glucose and other impurities and was pure as determined by its melting point (197-98°).

N/2 solutions of different nitrates (100 c.c) and glucose (5 g.) were exposed to sunlight in open 250 c.c. pyrex glass beakers and it was observed that in the absence of a photosensitiser, practically no amino acid is obtained. Amongst the photosensitisers, titania is the best ; uranium ammonium carbonate acts as a feeble photosensitiser in the formation of amino acid from nitrates and glucose. In the following experiments, 1 g. of titania was added and the mixture stirred from time to time and 5 c.c. of the solution withdrawn and filtered and the amino acid formed was estimated colorimetrically by adding ninhydrin. The following results have been obtained.

TABLE I.

Time.	Amounts of amino acid formed with		
	<i>N/2-NH₄NO₃</i> .	<i>N/2-NaNO₃</i> .	<i>N/2-KNO₃</i> .
2 hr.	0	0	0·00012 <i>N</i>
4	0·00005 <i>N</i>	0·00027 <i>N</i>	0·00040
6	0·00125	0·00040	0·00084
8	0·00109	0·00024	0·00110
10	0·00053	0·00020	0·00034
12	0·00000	0·00018	0·00027
Dark	0	0	0

The foregoing results show that the amount of α -amino acids photosynthesised from glucose and nitrates in presence of titania, is maximum with ammonium nitrate and minimum with sodium nitrate. Moreover, the amount of α -amino acids photosynthesised reaches a maximum value with increase of exposure and then falls off on further exposure. After 15-20 hours' exposure, practically no amino acid is detected, probably due to their photo-oxidation. It is interesting to note that no amino acid is obtained from glucose and

nitrates and titania when kept in the dark for several days, but in diffused light, appreciable amounts of amino acids are formed in open shallow porcelain dishes. When $N/2-NH_4OH$ or NH_4Cl or $N/2-(NH_4)_2 SO_4$ is substituted for nitrates, no amino acid is photosynthesised in this way, although plants like barley, rice, maize and pumpkins, which are rich in carbohydrates, readily take up ammonium salts.

The effect of the addition of differently coloured inorganic salts (0.5 g. in each case) to a mixture of glucose (4%), $N/2$ -potassium nitrate and titania (1 g.) was also investigated and the results are as follows.

TABLE II.

	Time → 4 hrs.	8 hrs.	12 hrs.	Dark
Uranium acetate	0.00014 N	0.00054 N	0.00007 N	0
Cobalt chloride	0.00014	0.00053	0.00007	0
Copper sulphate	0.00013	0.00040	0.00005	0
Nickel sulphate	0.00013	0.00040	0.00005	0
No coloured salt	0.00012	0.00035	0.00003	0

These results show that increased light absorption by the mixtures, increases the amounts of amino acid photosynthesised.

The results in Table III show that ferrous sulphate increases the yield of amino acid but sodium phosphate or calcium carbonate is without any influence.

TABLE III.

0.5 G. of each reagent added.

Time.	Sodium phosphate.	Calcium carbonate.	Ferrous sulphate.	No reagent.
4 hr.	0.00014N	0.00014N	0.00021N	0.00014N
6	0.00021	0.00021	0.00028	0.00021
8	0.00035	0.00035	0.00049	0.00034
10	0.00035	0.00035	0.00028	0.00034
12	0.00014	0.00014	0.00008	0.00014
Dark	0	0	0	0

It seems that the photo-oxidation of amino acids on prolonged exposures is facilitated by ferrous sulphate, as the amounts of amino acids decrease more readily in its presence when the exposure is prolonged.

In the following tables, the influence of the variation in the amounts of nitrates, glucose and titania has been investigated.

TABLE IV.

4 G. of glucose and 1 g. TiO_2 used.

Exposed for	→ 6 hrs.	8 hrs.	10 hrs.
$\bar{N}/2.5\text{-KNO}_3$	0.00035N	0.00084N	0.00027
N/5	0.00035	0.00083	0.00029
N/10	0.00035	0.00082	0.00031
N/20	0.00034	0.00082	0.00032
N/40	0.00029	...	0.00035
N/80	0.00029	...	0.00022
N/160	0	...	traces
N/320	0	...	0

TABLE V.

2 G. of KNO_3 and 1 g. of TiO_2 used.

glucose (g.) ...	4	2	1	0.5	0.25	0.125	0.0625
Time { 6 hrs. ...	0.00039N	0.00035	0.00028	0.00022	0.00014	0.00007	0.00003
{ 8 hrs. ...	0.00060N	0.00030	0.00007	0	0	0	0

2 G. of Glucose and 1 g. of KNO_3 used.

TiO_2 (g.) ...	3	2	1	0
Time { 6 hrs. ...	0.00039N	0.00035	0.00028	0.00007
{ 8 hrs. ...	0.00051N	0.00019	0.00042	0.00022

The results recorded in Tables IV and V show that after the limiting concentration $N/80$, the amount of amino acid photosynthesised increases slightly with increase of potassium nitrate concentration. When the concentration of KNO_3 is $N/160$ or smaller, practically no amino acid is photosynthesised.

The amount of amino acid produced increases appreciably with increase in the glucose concentration. Increase of titania also increases the photosynthesis.

In order to find out whether the products of the reaction affect the activity of the titania surface, the following experiments were

performed. Three beakers A, B, C each containing 2 g. of glucose, 2 g. of KNO_3 and 1 g. titania were exposed to sunlight. The beaker A was left undisturbed. The solution in beaker B was changed after 8 hours' exposure and fresh solution of the same concentration was put in. In beaker C, after 8 hours' exposure, the titania was replaced by the same amount of fresh titania. The amounts of amino acid photosynthesised are recorded in Table VI.

TABLE VI.

	Time → 8 hrs.	12 hrs.	14 hrs.
A. Glucose (2 g.) + KNO_3 (2 g.) + TiO_2 (1 g.)	0.00035 N	0.00022 N	0.00007 N
B. Same TiO_2 but new solution after 8 hrs.	—	0.00007	0
C. Same solution but fresh TiO_2 after 8 hrs.	—	0.00043	0.00049

It seems that the surface of titania in contact with the exposed solution becomes ineffective probably due to the adsorption of the products of the reaction.

Not only glucose but fructose, mannose, galactose and arabinose when exposed to sunlight with potassium nitrate and titania yield amino acids. Moreover, substances, which on exposure to light form reducing sugars readily, also produce amino acids with KNO_3 , as is evident from the following table.

TABLE VII.

$N/2$ - KNO_3 and 1 g. of TiO_2 with 5% solutions of the following.

	Tartaric acid.	Glycerol.	Glycol.	Lactic acid.	Citric acid.	Malic acid.
Time { 8 hrs.	0.00039 N	0.00046 N	0.00036 N	0	0	0
{ 12 hrs.	0.00001 N	0.00002 N	0.00002 N	0	0	0

With lactic, citric and malic acids, reducing sugars can be detected by Fehling's or Benedict's solution only after long exposures, whereas with glycerol, glycol and tartaric acid, sugars are detected even after an exposure of 30 minutes with potassium nitrate and titania.

It is known that ammonium lactate forms alanine in the animal body. On exposing 3% solution of ammonium lactate with titania, amino acid is detected after five hours. On the other hand, ammonium tartrate, ammonium malate, ammonium citrate and

a mixture of ammonia and glycerol even after 30 hours' exposure to sunlight do not produce any amino acid.

Attempts were made to isolate the amino acids formed in photosynthesis from (a) mixtures of 50 c. c. glycol and 20 g. of potassium nitrate, and (b) mixtures of 20 g. glucose and 20 g. of potassium nitrate in presence of 10 g. of titania per litre of solution exposed in open shallow porcelain dishes to sunlight for 6—8 hours. It was suspected that glycine would be formed from glycol and arginine from glucose.

(a) *With glycol.*—The exposed solution was filtered to free it from titania and was concentrated under vacuum on a water-bath. The amount of amino acid formed was estimated colorimetrically and an equivalent amount of sodium carbonate was added and followed by the addition of excess of mercuric acetate solution and a stream of CO_2 was passed. The precipitate obtained was filtered and to the solution, alcohol was added to precipitate the mercury salt of glycine carbonate, which was first washed thoroughly with alcohol and then with cold distilled water. H_2S was passed to liberate the amino acid and the excess of H_2S removed by a current of hydrogen. On evaporation glycine separates out (*cf.* Neuberg and Kerb, *Biochem. Z.*, 1912, 40, 498; Siegfried Schutt, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1912, 72, 260). This method yields the amino acid, which has to be further purified by dissolving it in water and treating the solution with alcohol and $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ and a stream of CO_2 (*cf.* Kingston and Schryver, *Biochem. J.*, 1924, 18, 1070). The precipitate was filtered and washed with alcohol and then with cold water. The glycine was extracted with hot water from the barium carbonate, which was filtered off. On evaporation, crystals were left.

The amino acid gave a strong blue coloration with ninhydrin and a red coloration with ferric chloride and a blue colour with phenol and sodium hypochlorite. These are important tests for glycine. The melting point of the crystals varied from 220° to 228° (m. p. of glycine, 225° — 230°). Glycine forms a soluble copper salt, which was prepared and dried and ignited and weighed as CuO . From 0.1170 g. of the copper salt 0.0385 g. CuO was obtained in one experiment giving a molecular weight of 80.1 for the amino acid (theoretical 75).

(b) *With glucose.*—As in the former case (*cf.* Neuberg and Kerb, *loc. cit.*) the amino acid was first purified by decomposing the mercury salt with H_2S ; but in this case, the amino acid is

contaminated with glycuronic acid. To purify the amino acid further, flavianic acid was added to the solution and kept in the cold for 3 days. The crystals obtained were washed in cold water and again purified by recrystallisation. The melting points of different samples varied from 257° to 270°, when there was carbonisation. The m. p. of arginine flavinate is about 260° (cf. Kossel and Gross, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1924, 135, 167).

In order to isolate the amino acid, the flavinate was dissolved in 33% hot H_2SO_4 and the sulphonic acid was removed by extraction with butyl alcohol. The aqueous solution was treated with $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ in excess and saturated with CO_2 and filtered. The filtrate on evaporation yields an amino acid, which sinters at 234° and carbonises at 240° and gives the tests for arginine. Further work on the isolation of the amino acids in the pure state is in progress.

The experimental results recorded above show that small amounts of amino acids are readily formed *in vitro* by the interaction of nitrates and carbohydrates, or substances which produce carbohydrates, readily when exposed to sunlight in presence of suitable catalysts and photosensitisers and no amino acid is synthesised in the dark.

In plants, not only six membered carbohydrates but six membered amino acids, such as leucine, arginine, lysine, histidine, tryptophan and cystine chiefly occur in plant proteins. Amongst the amino acids obtained from the plant proteins, arginine occurs in the largest amount. We have been able to obtain evidence of arginine formation from glucose and nitrates and titania in presence of sunlight. It seems, therefore, that the amino acids in plants are synthesised from carbohydrates and nitrates and that sunlight is an important agency in this reaction and the plant pigments are likely to behave as sensitisers, just as titania and uranium salts sensitise the process *in vitro*.

In previous publications (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 287, 699) it has been observed that aqueous solutions of amino acids are readily oxidised to ammonia and carbon dioxide and other products in presence of light and air. It appears, that the amino acids obtained in photosynthesis are oxidised by potassium nitrate or oxygen of the air in presence of sunlight and thus the photosynthesised amino acids disappear on longer exposure.

Recently it has been observed by us that the constancy C:N ratio (10:1) not only exists in the soil but is also observed in animal

metabolism and when a mixture of organic compounds containing nitrogenous substances present in natural systems undergo oxidation in air, a constant ratio of carbon to nitrogen is finally attained (results communicated to this journal for publication).

In the plant, protein synthesis takes place only when carbohydrates are present, because the reaction between nitrate and carbohydrate causes the liberation of energy, which seems to be indispensable for protein synthesis and that is why most plants cannot utilise ammonium salts directly because of the lack of the energy available from the reaction of the carbohydrates and nitrates. It has been stated that the rice plants take up ammonium salts in the beginning of its development and nitrates in the end. It seems that in the case of rice and other carbohydrate producing plants, in the beginning they contain large amounts of carbohydrate and little protein and thus the C:N ratio may be much greater than 10:1 and hence the ammonia is absorbed; whilst in the end, protein accumulation takes place due to the energy supplied by the oxidation of the carbohydrates and then the ratio of C:N tends to the value 10:1 and that is why ammonium salts are not required. Legumes, lupins and beans, however, should at no stage grow with ammonium salts. On the other hand, starch and other carbohydrate producing plants at certain stages, when the carbohydrate content is very high and protein content low, may be fed and made to grow well by ammonium salts.

It is stated that the case of ammonia assimilation by plants depends on the rate with which it is converted into asparagine and this in turn depends on the amount of carbohydrates, the other class of substances necessary for protein synthesis.

SUMMARY.

1. Small amounts of α -amino acids are photosynthesised by exposing solutions of glucose and nitrates in presence of titania to sunlight. The yield is greater with nitrates of ammonium and potassium than sodium. Longer exposure causes the disappearance of the amino acids, due to their photo-oxidation.

2. Coloured inorganic salts cause an increase of photosynthesis but CaCO_3 and sodium phosphate are without influence.

3. Increase in the amounts of glucose or titania causes more photosynthesis than an increase in the amount of KNO_3 . Other carbohydrates such as fructose, galactose, arabinose etc., and

substances which on exposure to light produce reducing sugars yield also readily, amino acids. Ammonium lactate on exposure to light with *tatania* forms amino acid.

4. It seems that glycine from glycol and KNO_3 and TiO_2 , and arginine from glucose, KNO_3 and TiO_2 , are formed along with other substances from photosynthesis and attempts have been made to isolate these two amino acids.

5. It has been found that *in vitro* ammonium salts and carbohydrates do not form amino acids in light. It seems that protein synthesis in plants and *in vitro* is facilitated by the energy obtained from the oxidation of carbohydrates by nitrates or oxygen of the air. An explanation has been offered why carbohydrate-producing plants can grow in the presence of ammonium salts, and it is believed that the absorption of ammonium ion or nitrate ion by a plant is controlled mainly by the ratio C:N in it.

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